

STRENGTH OF SiC- AND Si-N-C-CERAMIC FIBERS EXPOSED TO
HIGH-TEMPERATURE GASEOUS ENVIRONMENTS*

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ABSTRACT

The effects of exposures to high-temperature gaseous environments on the strengths of Nicalon SiC fiber and HPZ Si-N-C fiber were investigated. The exposure conditions included: (1) Ar with various P_{O_2} at 1000° and 1200°C for 10 h, and (2) air at 1000°, 1200°, and 1400°C for times up to 100 h. Individual fibers were tested in tension at room temperature following exposure, and correlations were made between the measured strengths and observed changes in surface morphology including that of the fracture surfaces. Thermal degradation of both fibers occurred under all conditions investigated. In fact, the effect of temperature far outweighed the effect of any other variable including the level of oxidant in the atmosphere, or exposure time. Although of significantly different chemistry, degree of crystallinity (Nicalon is crystalline, HPZ is amorphous), and cross-sectional geometry, the strengths of the fibers and their response to the various exposures were remarkably similar with one exception. The strength of the HPZ fiber was significantly less degraded by exposure in air at 1400°C for times greater than two hours.

KEY WORDS: Silicon Carbide/Silicon Carbonitride Fibers; Gaseous Environments; Corrosion; Strength; Characterization.

1. INTRODUCTION

There is increasing interest in the use of continuous ceramic fibers as reinforcing agents in both metal- and ceramic-matrix composite materials which can be lighter, stronger, and tougher than their monolithic counterparts.(1-6) Organometallic polymer-derived fibers such as Nicalon® SiC

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fiber* and DOW CORNING® X9-6371 HPZ Ceramic Fiber† are among the leading candidate materials for such purposes.(7,8) The materials are fabricated by similar processing techniques and sequences. The fibers begin as organosilicon polymers that are melt-spun into polymer fibers. The polymer fibers are cured, and subsequently converted into ceramic fibers by heat treatment. The polycarbosilane polymer precursor of the Nicalon fiber is heat treated in vacuum at about 1300°C.(7) The resulting fiber consists of microcrystalline β -SiC plus significant amounts of free SiO₂ and C.(9,10) The Nicalon fibers have a circular cross section with an average diameter (as measured in this study) of $14.0 \pm 1.0 \mu\text{m}$. The Nicalon material is a mature fiber that has been extensively studied. The experimental HPZ fiber is the result of a more recent effort whose goal was to develop a ceramic fiber with composition approaching that of Si₃N₄.(8) The precursor of the HPZ fiber is hydridopolysilazane (thus HPZ). The spun polymer fiber is converted to the ceramic by pyrolysis in N₂ at 1200°C. According to the manufacturer's information sheet, the resulting fiber is amorphous, with a typical composition of 57 Si-10 C-28 N-4 O, wt %. About half of the carbon is present in a microcrystalline graphitic structure. The HPZ fiber has an oval cross section. The average major and minor diameters of the material in this study were $14.0 \pm 1.0 \mu\text{m}$ and $8.0 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$, respectively.

Since ceramic fibers may be exposed to high temperature environments during fabrication and service, a thorough understanding of the high-temperature stability and corrosion behavior of these materials is of critical importance for many applications. Previous investigations have considered the effects of thermal and environmental exposures on the stability of Nicalon SiC fiber. We were unable to find any published environmental studies on HPZ fiber. As far as Nicalon fiber is concerned, the changes in microstructure and mechanical properties have been monitored as functions of heat treatments in various environments including air, argon, nitrogen, and vacuum, and at various temperatures and pressures.(4,9-16) Nonetheless, one important variable, the effect of oxidant level in the ambient gases, has not been fully investigated. We previously observed that the strengths of bulk SiC (17,18) and Si₃N₄ (19) exposed to high temperature gaseous atmospheres was very sensitive to the level of oxidant (P_{H₂O} in H₂ or P_{O₂} in Ar) in the environment. Even small variations in oxidant level in the ambient gases caused the strengths after exposure to vary remarkably. However, unlike bulk SiC or Si₃N₄, both the Nicalon and HPZ fibers contain significant amounts of free carbon, and the Nicalon also free SiO₂. Therefore, their corrosion behavior in inert atmospheres containing various amounts of oxidants would be expected to be different from that of bulk SiC or Si₃N₄ materials. In addition, in most of the previous air exposure tests on Nicalon fibers the researchers employed only one exposure time (typically less than 10 h), which hampers the drawing of definitive conclusions regarding the effects of exposure time on the mechanical properties of this fiber.

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In this paper, we present some of the initial results of an investigation on the high temperature stability of Nicalon SiC and HPZ Si-N-C fibers in various gaseous atmospheres. The environments studied were neutral-to-oxidizing (Ar with various P_{O_2}), and fully oxidizing (air) over a range of temperatures (1000°, 1200°, and 1400°C) and exposure times (2-100 h). The room-temperature tensile strengths of individual fibers were measured after each exposure. The observed variations in strength were related to the morphological changes that resulted from the thermal- and environmental-exposures.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Material Preparation and Exposure Commercially available Nicalon fibers (NLM-202, ceramic grade) and experimental X9-6371 HPZ fibers were used in these experiments. Both fibers were received as tows containing approximately 500 fibers. Sizings on the fibers were removed by immersing the fibers in ultrasonically agitated baths of acetone and isopropyl alcohol. Groups of 20 fibers were exposed to the following atmospheres and conditions: (1) Ar with various P_{O_2} for 10 h at 1000° and 1200°C, and (2) air for 2 to 100 h at 1000°, 1200°, and 1400°C. The heat treatments in Ar- O_2 atmospheres were performed in a resistance-heated, horizontal alumina-tube furnace. For air exposures, a box furnaces with rapid heating and cooling capability was used. The P_{O_2} in the Ar atmospheres was controlled by mixing Ar and O_2 gases, and measured with an oxygen analyzer.† The gas mixtures were purified with $CaSO_4$ and activated alumina, and flowed with a constant speed of 0.9 cm/s (STP) at a total pressure of about 0.1 MPa (slightly higher than 1 atm). Rectangular alumina crucibles with a series of slots on two opposing edges, was used to support twenty individual fibers during each exposure. The portion of the fibers to be tested did not contact either the crucible or each other during exposure.

2.2 Fiber Mounting and Testing Support frames fabricated from 35 mm slide mounts were used to facilitate handling of the fibers after exposure and provide a means for alignment in the testing machine. Prior to attachment of a fiber, a slide mount was placed in a jig and drilled to ultimately accept small pins in the load train of the test system, and scribed with a shallow groove to insure fiber alignment. The center line of the groove passed through the center lines of the pin holes at either end of the frame, and parallel with the load axis. The mounts were then cut in half along a line perpendicular to the load axis. The resulting halves of each mount were held together, and in alignment, by metal binding clips that were carefully removed only when the sample was safely loaded in the testing machine. The ends of each fiber were bonded with an adhesive* in the groove scribed in the surface of the frame. The gauge length of the fibers so mounted was 25.4 mm. The diameter of each mounted fiber was measured using an optical microscope† equipped with a filar eyepiece. The filar eyepiece was calibrated using a precision

† Model S-3A, Applied Electrochemistry Inc., Sunnyvale, CA.

* Steven Industries, Bayonne, NJ.

† Labophot-2A, Nikon Corp., Tokyo, Japan.

graticule.** The diameter of each Nicalon fiber was taken to be the average of three to five measured values. The oval nature of the cross section of the HPZ fibers made diametral measurement more difficult. The HPZ fibers are apparently twisted during manufacture so that when scanned along the gauge length the major and minor diameters are periodically visible. Three major and three minor diameters were measured on each fiber. On examination of the fracture surface of tested fibers, it was seen that the cross-section was more the shape of a rectangle with semicircular ends than an ellipse. Accordingly, in this study the cross-sectional area A of the HPZ fibers was calculated as:

$$A = (D - d)d + \frac{\pi d^2}{4}$$

where D and d are the major and minor diameters, respectively.

The fibers were tested in tension at room temperature using a screw-driven universal testing machine at a crosshead speed of 0.05 cm/min. Small diameter "lamp-pull" chains, and miniature swivel hooks were used in the load train to minimize the bending loads on the fibers. Specimen load was sensed by a 1000 g capacity load cell that was mechanically calibrated by standard balance weights prior to each series of tests. Calibration was rechecked at the conclusion of each test set. Ten fibers were tested following exposure at each set of environmental conditions. Because the fibers fractured at loads ranging from only about 5 to 60 g, depending on exposure conditions, the load frame of the testing machine was enclosed to minimize the effects of air currents on the test results. Following each test the fragments of the fiber were collected so that the surface of selected samples could be examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Nicalon Fiber Exposed to Ar-O₂ Atmospheres Significant reductions in tensile strength were observed in the Nicalon fibers exposed to Ar atmospheres with various P_{O₂} levels. The average strengths of the fibers after exposure for 10 h to Ar at 1000° and 1200°C as a function of oxygen partial pressure of the exposure atmosphere are shown in Fig. 1. These data show that the strength decreased from 2830 ± 870 MPa (average and standard deviation for 30 fibers) for the as-received fibers, to about 1760 ± 300 MPa for the fibers exposed at 1000°C to Ar atmospheres with the lowest P_{O₂} level. The decrease in strength was more severe following exposure at 1200°C, dropping to about 1300 ± 340 MPa. At both temperatures the strength after exposure was relatively independent of (or at least not dramatically dependent on) the P_{O₂} level. Such behavior implies that, at these temperatures, the observed degradation of the fibers was mainly due to thermal effects rather than corrosion. However, although not prominent, there does appear to be some indication of the typically observed (in bulk SiC) transition from active oxidation at low P_{O₂} levels to passive oxidation when the oxidation level is increased. We previously observed that the strength or weight of SiC drops dramatically in the active oxidation

** Graticules Ltd., Tonbridge, Kent, England.

regime and recovers just as dramatically after the transition to passive oxidation.(18) The fact that such transition is not very distinct in these data may be attributable to the relatively low temperatures of the exposures. The growth of surface flaws as the result of reactions between free C and SiO₂, or SiC and SiO₂, both of which generate CO(g) and SiO(g), and growth of the β-SiC crystallite grains were previously identified as the thermal-degradation mechanisms in this material.(9,15,16)

An SEM micrograph of a fracture surface of a typical Nicalon fiber after sizing removal, Fig. 2 (a), shows the surface flaw from which the fracture initiated as well as the mirror and hackle regions associated with brittle fracture. A typical fracture surface of fibers exposed for 10 h at 1200°C to Ar with P_{O₂} = 1.1 × 10⁻⁵ MPa [Fig. 2 (b)] shows pits formed by the active oxidation process. These pits are believed to be responsible for further reductions in strength (in addition to the thermally-induced reduction) of the fibers exposed at the lower oxygen levels. When the P_{O₂} was increased to 5 × 10⁻⁵ MPa, which is within the passive oxidation region, a thin layer of SiO₂ is presumed to have been formed on the surface. However, the silica layer is not observed clearly apparently due to its meager thickness [Fig. 2 (c)] Thick layers of SiO₂ were observed on the fibers exposed to environments with higher P_{O₂}, i.e., air, as will be discussed below. Even though not thick enough to be observed by SEM, this layer is believed to protect the fiber from further oxidation, and at the same time, to blunt the cracks and flaws that decrease strength of the fibers. A similar dependency of strength on the P_{O₂} level in Ar atmospheres was observed for bulk α-SiC exposed to similar conditions.(18)

3.2 HPZ Fiber Exposed to Ar-O₂ Atmospheres Significant reductions in tensile strength were likewise observed in the HPZ fibers exposed to Ar atmospheres with various P_{O₂} levels as shown in Fig. 1. The data for the 1000°C heat treatments show that the strength decreased from 2900 ± 410 MPa (average and standard deviation for 15 fibers) for the HPZ fibers after sizing removal, to about 1350 ± 275 MPa for the fibers exposed at the lowest P_{O₂} level (8 × 10⁻⁷ MPa). The strength was decreased to a very similar value by exposure at 1200°C to an Ar atmosphere with P_{O₂} = 7.6 × 10⁻⁷ MPa. The fact that the strength of this fiber was essentially the same after exposure at either temperature (whereas the Nicalon fiber was more severely degraded at the higher temperature) seem to imply that the HPZ fiber is a more thermally stable material. As was the case with the Nicalon fiber, there was a perceptible, but not dramatic, influence of P_{O₂} level on the strength of this fiber.

The SEM micrographs of the fracture surfaces of typical HPZ fibers in Fig. 3, show the morphology of this fiber is similar to the Nicalon except for the obvious difference in cross-sectional geometry. Remnants of the sizing material, polyvinyl alcohol, are seen on the exterior of the unexposed fiber shown in Fig. 3 (a). The micrograph in Fig. 3 (b) shows a fiber that was exposed for 10 h at 1200°C in an argon atmosphere with P_{O₂} = 7.6 × 10⁻⁷ MPa. The fact that the surface of this is essentially featureless indicates that this exposure condition was in the active oxidation regime. A "patch" of corrosion product is visible on the side of the fiber

exposed under the same conditions but with an oxygen level of 4.4×10^{-5} MPa, Fig. 3 (c). This material, evidently SiO_2 , is locally thicker and rougher in regions associated with pores just at the surface, one of which has initiated fracture in this specimen. Such localized corrosion product areas were also evident in the Nicalon fiber exposed under similar conditions, Fig.2 (c)

3.3 Nicalon Fiber Exposed to Air The average room temperature tensile strengths of the Nicalon fibers exposed in air at elevated temperatures were very significantly affected by exposure temperature, but less significantly affected by time at temperature. The strengths of the fibers exposed to air at 1000°, 1200°, and 1400°C for times up to 100 h are shown in Fig. 4. At all three exposure temperatures, the strength of the fiber was initially reduced rapidly with increasing exposure time for the first 2 to 5 h and then displayed either a gain in strength or at least a much less rapid loss. The most notable example of a recovery in strength (after the initial drop during the first 5 h exposure) was in the fibers exposed at 1000°C. In this case, the fibers displayed the same strength (2000 MPa) after 30 h exposure as they did after only 2 h exposure. As the exposure was increased to 100 h at 1000°C, the fibers gradually lost strength but still not to the minimum level (1250 MPa) observed after 5 h exposure. Similar behavior occurred when the fibers were exposed at 1200°C, but the recovery in strength with increasing exposure time was not observed. Here the fibers decreased drastically in strength after the first 2 h of exposure, and then much more gradually with increasing time. The degradation of the fibers by exposure to air at 1400°C was, as expected, even more severe. The strength of the fibers decreased to 365 MPa after only 10 h exposure, and they were too fragile to test after longer exposure times. Such behavior is quite different from that observed by Mah et. al.(9) They reported a strength of 2110 MPa for Nicalon fiber after removal of a vinyl acetate sizing resin, and 1379 MPa after 2 h in air at 1400°C. This amounts to a strength reduction of only 35% compared to the approximately 65% reduction in strength observed in the present work for fibers exposed under the same conditions.

Simon and Bunsell (10) observed that when Nicalon fiber was exposed to high temperatures, the average grain size of the fibers increased rapidly for short exposure periods and remained constant thereafter. We believe that the rapid reductions in strength of the fibers observed in the present work are due to the combination of grain growth and the reaction between the SiO_2 and free C contained in the fibers. Simultaneously, a layer of silica forms on the surface of the fibers. As exposure time at a given temperature is increased, the silica layer on the surface became thicker and denser, as illustrated in a typical micrograph, Fig. 5 (a), of a fiber exposed for 50 h at 1200°C. We attribute the observed increases in (or retention of) strength with increasing exposure times to the progressive growth of this dense silica layer. We believe that the role of the SiO_2 layer is to minimize the severity of surface flaws and to retard the reaction between the free SiO_2 and free carbon in the fiber by restricting outward transport of the product gases. However, when the silica layer became too thick as a result of exposure for times >50 h, or at higher temperatures new flaws (such as bubbles or cracks) are formed as shown by a

typical micrograph in Fig. 6 (a) of a fiber exposed for 10 h at 1400°C. The gradual reductions in strength over long exposure times are apparently due to the formation of these new flaws.

3.4 HPZ Fiber Exposed to Air The strengths of the HPZ fibers exposed at 1000° and 1200°C generally decreased in parallel to those of the Nicalon fibers. However, as seen in Fig. 4, for exposure times less than 50 h the HPZ fibers did retain more of their original strength than did the Nicalon material exposed under the same or similar conditions.

Examination of the tested samples using SEM showed that the morphologies of the two type of fibers were similar after the various exposures as can be seen by comparing the two micrographs in Fig. 5. The micrograph in Fig. 5 (b) of an HPZ fiber exposed in air for 50 h at 1200°C shows that a relatively thick, but dense and "defect free" layer has formed on the surface. As it did in the case of the Nicalon fiber, we assume that this corrosion product serves to isolate the fiber from the atmosphere and retard further attack.

An interesting finding of this work is the observation that although the behavior of the two fibers was similar on exposure to air at 1000°C and 1200°C, their behaviors diverged very significantly when the exposures were at 1400°C. The strength of the HPZ fiber after exposure for 10 h at 1400°C was still 1100 ± 280 MPa as compared to the strength of the Nicalon material 365 ± 60 MPa. In fact, the strength of the HPZ after 10 h exposure was apparently even greater than after 2 h exposure, 950 ± 375 MPa. This very different behavior was well explained when the fibers were examined by SEM. As can be seen in Fig. 6 (b), the HPZ fiber had not developed the rough, cracked surface seen on the Nicalon fiber, and there was no evidence of the large pores beneath the surface. The appearance of the HPZ fiber after 10 h at 1400°C was not much different from that of the fiber exposed for 50 h at 1200°C, Fig. 5 (b), and accordingly their strengths were also similar.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The room temperature tensile strengths of Nicalon SiC and X9-6371 HPZ Si-N-C fibers following exposure to high-temperature environments were influenced by both the exposure atmosphere and temperature. The fibers were subject to thermal degradation regardless of the exposure environment, as indicated by the observed reductions in strength even on exposure to high-purity Ar atmospheres. However, in addition to the thermal effect, a noticeable, though not dramatic transition from active-to-passive oxidation was observed in Ar-O₂ atmospheres. When a silica layer was formed on the surface of the fibers, reductions in strength were minimal. When exposed to air at 1000° and 1200°C, the strengths of the fibers decreased rapidly for exposure times of 2 to 5 h and then either gained strength or at least decreased much less rapidly thereafter. The formation of a dense silica layer on the surface was apparently responsible for the observed retention in strength at longer exposure times. Similar behavior occurred in the HPZ fibers exposed to air at 1400°C. The strength of this fiber was still 1100 ± 280 MPa after exposure to air for 10 h at 1400°C. This strength retention was very significant in light of the

fact that after the same exposure the strength of the Nicalon fiber was only 365 ± 60 MPa. Examination of the exposed Nicalon fibers revealed that the beneficial role of the silica layer was mitigated when the layer became too thick and consequently new flaws (such as bubbles and cracks) were formed either within the layer or at the interface between the fiber and the surface layer.

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FIGURE 1. Room temperature tensile strengths of Nicalon and HPZ fibers exposed for 10 h to Ar-O₂ atmospheres at 1000° and 1200°C. Each data point and error bar represent average and one standard deviation of 10 specimens, respectively.

FIGURE 2. SEM micrographs of Nicalon fibers: (a) before exposure and after exposure at 1200°C for 10 h to Ar with different P_{O_2} level, (b) $P_{O_2} = 1.1 \times 10^{-5}$ MPa, (c) $P_{O_2} = 5 \times 10^{-5}$ MPa.

FIGURE 3. SEM micrographs of HPZ fibers: (a) before exposure and after exposure at 1200°C for 10 h to Ar with P_{O_2} level, (b) $P_{O_2} = 7.6 \times 10^{-7}$ MPa, (c) $P_{O_2} = 4.4 \times 10^{-5}$ MPa.

FIGURE 4. Room temperature tensile strengths of Nicalon and HPZ fibers exposed to air for 10 h at 1000°C to 1400°C. Each data point and error bar represent average and one standard deviation of 10 specimens, respectively.

FIGURE 5. SEM micrographs of (a) Nicalon and (b) HPZ fibers exposed for 50 h to air at 1200°C.

FIGURE 6. SEM micrographs of (a) Nicalon and (b) HPZ fibers exposed to air at 1400°C for 10 h.

